

Performance Study and Comparison Between Wired and Wireless Charging for Smartphone Applications

Matthew Zhang

Valley Christian High School, San Jose, California, USA

ABSTRACT

Wireless charging has recently become a common feature of many high-end consumer electronics such as smartphones. It offers the convenience of not having to insert a charging cable manually. However, wireless charging comes with a price on charging performance that needs to be clearly quantified. This article compares the performances of both wired and wireless charging methods. It aims to arm you with experimented data to decide which charging method better aligns with your digital lifestyle.

Keywords: Wireless charging, Thermal stress, Electromagnetic induction, MagSafe charger, Qi standard

1. INTRODUCTION

Wireless connections have become a trend in the past few decades of consumer electronics, ranging from earphones (wired vs. Bluetooth) to internet (wired vs. WiFi) applications. As we increasingly rely on electronics for both personal and professional use, devices have been gradually designed with greater conveniences. If you look at a standard work desk, you may find many electrical power cables, for computers, monitors, and even chargers for mobile devices. Wireless power charging pits itself against traditional wired charging with the growing appeal of a cable-free experience. With smartphones as the leading example: almost all high-end phones from leading brands, such as Apple, Samsung, and Google (Pixel) offer wireless charging. However, in daily use, wireless charging has not become popular yet. Thus the question arises: which charging method is better for you?

1.1 Wired Charging

Wired charging has been the standard method for decades. It requires a physical connection between a DC power source and your electronic device. Nowadays the DC power source usually is a wall adapter with USB output ports. The process is straightforward. Plug the power adaptor into an AC source (like a wall outlet), attach the cable to the adaptor USB port, and connect the cable to your device. Electricity is passed from the outlet to the smartphone via the cable.

Figure 1. Wired Charging Conceptual Block Diagram

Figure 1 shows the conceptual block diagram of the wired charging of a smartphone. The power comes from an AC line, typically $110V_{rms}$ in the United States and $220V_{rms}$ in most other places. An AC-to-DC power converter, or wall adapter, is used to convert the AC voltage into lower voltage DC output voltage. The output of a modern adapter is usually a USB-A or USB-C port, with a DC voltage of 5V and can be up to 20V (USB-C). The wall adapter also provides galvanic isolation so the output ports are insulated from the high-voltage AC line, to guarantee the safety of users. With a wired connection, a USB cable is needed to connect the output of the wall adapter to the smartphone USB input charging port. There are different types of USB cables: Apple devices usually require a USB-to-Lighting port cable but recently with the new iPhone 15 they have begun using a USB-C cable. Most modern Android devices need a USB-C input cable, however, older Android devices have used micro-USB cables.

Regardless, inside the smartphone, the USB input port is connected to an internal battery charger DC-to-DC converter, which takes the USB input and generates a controlled DC current to charge the internal Lithium-ion battery. The Lithium-ion battery operates in a voltage range from 3.2V (almost fully discharged) to 4.2V (fully charged). There are many downstream DC/DC power converters inside the phone to convert the wide-range battery voltage to all required, tightly regulated voltages, ranging from 5V to as low as 0.5V for different devices inside a cell phone.

Just intuitively, wired charging is viewed as a reliable and efficient way to deliver electrical energy from the wall adapter to the cell phone. It uses only a connection cable with minimum additional connection resistance and subsequent power loss. A properly sized cable can deliver higher power (up to 20W of a modern phone) to speed up charging time in recent years. Furthermore, the USB-C port standard can support up to 100W. So conceptually, wired charging can be fast and is only limited by the phone's internal charger power capability rather than the charging cable. On the other hand, wired charging can be less convenient because manual insertion is always required. Another inconvenience is people often require specialized USB cables for different devices. The cell phone charging port also has a limited lifetime. A bad connection may happen after a few years of use as the charging port reaches its maximum number of insertions and becomes loose. With time, the device will become unusable.

Wireless Charging

Wireless charging is defined as electrical energy being delivered wirelessly without a direct, physical cable connection between the charger and the charging device. In the case of smartphone charging, the charger is a charging pad and the device is a smartphone. As manual cable insertion action is not required, it is viewed (or at least marketed) as more convenient compared to wired charging.

To implement wireless electrical energy transfer, additional devices and power conversion stages are required. Figure 2 shows the conceptual block diagram of a wireless charging system using the same cell phone example. Connected to the wall adapter DC output, an additional wireless charging pad is used to convert the DC power to a higher frequency AC power. To achieve compatibility with different charging pads, consumer electronics usually follow the “Qi Standard” for wireless charging. In this case, the charging pad generates AC power running at a 110kHz to 200kHz frequency. The power converter generating the AC power from the DC source is also called an inverter. The output side of the inverter is a power transmitter coil. With high-frequency AC current going through the transmitter coil, AC magnetic flux is generated. On the other side, inside the smartphone, there is a matching receiver coil. Figure 3 shows the example pictures of a transmitter core and a receiver coil. As the receiver coil is placed right on top of the transmitter coil, the AC magnetic flux from the transmitter coil induces AC current in the power receiver coil. In this case, the transmitter coil and receiver coil are closely coupled and function just as a transformer. Therefore, AC electrical energy is passed from the transmitter coil to the receiver coil by AC magnetic flux, without a physical wired cable connection. Inside the phone, the receiver coil is connected to a rectifier circuit to convert AC current into DC current again. An additional filter network is necessary to remove the 110kHz-205kHz AC ripples, so the output will be a constant DC power to the DC-to-DC battery charger stage.

Figure 2. A conceptual Block Diagram of a Wireless Charging System (Cell Phone Example) with Additional Stages to Implement Wireless Energy Transfer

Figure 3. Wireless Charging Transmitting Coil and Receiving Coil Example Pictures.

Now we explained conceptually how wireless charging works. Additional DC/AC inverter, transmitter and receiver coils, and AC/DC rectifier stages are added to the power delivery path. Naturally, the additional stages may bring additional limitations or prices to the system:

- 1) Power capacity: the power delivery capability can be limited by the additional stages, primarily by the transmitter and receiving coils. In particular, the receiving coil is inside the cell phone, so its size and thickness are physically limited.
- 2) Coupling strength and alignments: to achieve good magnetic flux coupling, the transmitter coil and receiver coil have to be on top of each other and as close as possible. Their centers have to have decently good alignment.
- 3) Efficiency: additional power stages can also add additional power process loss and can hurt overall system efficiency.

These limitations could affect maximum charging power, therefore, increasing charging time and reducing energy efficiency.

2. METHODOLOGY

Experimental comparisons

To verify and quantify the performance effects of wireless charging, it is necessary to do side-by-side experimental comparisons between wired and wireless charging.

Experiment Setup:

In this experiment, the following devices are selected:

- 1) **Charger (Wall Adapter):** A 100W Baseus brand AC to USB wall adapter is selected as the DC USB voltage source. It is a high-performance adapter using the latest GaN power

transistor devices with high power density. It has two USB-C outputs (each supporting up to 100W as a single output source) and two USB-A style output ports (each supporting from 5V up to 20V, 60W). This adapter has a sufficient power rating, so it will not be a bottleneck limiting charging power to the cell phone. Therefore, the total charging power will be limited by either the cell phone’s internal charger or the wireless charging pad’s capacity.

- 2) **Wireless charging pad (transmitter):** Two wireless charging pads were selected for the experiment. The first one is Apple’s wireless MagSafe charging pad model #A2140, costing about \$40 in retail. Considering many consumers may choose a cheaper, non-Apple but Qi-compatible wireless charger, the author also tested an Anker Powerwave A2503 wireless charging pad. It is one of the top-rated Qi-compatible charging pads from Amazon.com with a price of only \$14 and over 123K reviews with a 4.5-star rating. This Anker pad is viewed as a good but cheap alternative to the original Apple A2140 pad.
- 3) **Smart Phone:** The iPhone 13 Model # MLA23LL/A with 128GB memory is used as the device under test (DUT). The iPhone 13 is selected mainly based on the available budget, as the author already owns this device. This phone is also sufficient to demonstrate the concept as it supports both wired charging with an Apple Lightning port and Qi-compatible wireless charging—both the original Apple charging pad and the Anker charging pad work with this phone.
- 4) **Charging Cable:** For the wired iPhone charger, the author selected a 3-foot-long USB-C to Lightning cable.
- 5) **Power measuring devices:** USB-based power meters are used to monitor real-time charging power from the wall adapter output port.

Figure 4. Two Different Wireless Charging Pads (transmitters) are Selected for the Experiment: 1) Apple MagSafe A2140 wireless charger; Retail price \$40; 2) Anker Qi-Compatible Powerwave A2503 wireless charger. Retail price \$14.

Wired charging setup

Figure 5 shows the wired charging setup. A small USB-C power Meter is inserted into the wall adapter output to monitor the current charging power. The iPhone 13 displays charging status in

terms of charge(%). The experiment will measure charging from 20% to 80% of the total battery capacity. During charging, charge time, charge(%), and power data will be collected for comparison.

Figure 5. Wired Charging Setup of an iPhone13 with a USB-C to Lightning Cable

Wireless charging setup

There are two setups with two different charging pads for comparison. Setup #1 uses the original Apple MagSafe wireless charging pad, as shown in Figure 6. Note the Apple Magsafe charger has a nice auto-alignment feature to align the transmitter center with the internal receiver coil on the back side of the iPhone. Therefore, maximum changing speed and efficiency can easily be achieved.

Figure 6. iPhone wireless charging setup with the Apple MagSafe Charger

Setup #2 uses the Qi-compatible Anker Powerwave charging pad, as shown in Figure 7. In this setup, the USB-A style port and power meter are used because the Anker pad requires a USB-A style cable. The Anker charger pad size is larger than the iPhone. It does not have the auto-alignment feature from the Apple MagSafe pad. So the iPhone should be carefully placed to align the center. It can be viewed on the power meter while adjusting placement to achieve the maximum charging current (power). Again, the iPhone screen displays the charging status in terms of charge(%).

Figure 7 iPhone wireless charging with the Anker Charging Pad

In all wired and wireless charging measurements, the charge time, charge(%), and real-time charging power were collected for comparison.

Wired and Wireless Comparison Results

1. **Charging time (Speed):** The first, and most meaningful comparison for users is charging time (speed). Figure 8 shows the charging time vs. charging status (%) plots of three different iPhone charging setups: 1) wired charging in the blue plot, 2) wireless charging with the Apple MagSafe charging pad in the red plot, and 3) wireless charging with the Qi-Compatible Anker charging pad in the green plot.

Figure 8 Charging Time vs. Charging % Comparison (iPhone 13)

As shown in Figure 8, the wired charging can charge the phone battery from 20% to 80% in about 40 minutes (1X), while it takes about 100 minutes (2.5X) for wireless charging with the \$40 Apple MagSafe pad and 150 minutes (3.75X) with the cheaper \$14 Anker Powerwave wireless charging pad. **In conclusion, wired charging is much faster than wireless charging!** Besides, the Apple wireless charging pad is much faster than the 3rd party Qi-compatible Anker charging pad, despite the great reviews of the Anker pad on Amazon.

The author also did another comparison to compare the wireless charging time using the Apple charger, with or without a protection case of the iPhone, considering many people usually put on a plastic protection case outside of their valuable iPhone. The case used on the iPhone 13 for testing is a “wireless charging compatible” case made in plastic but with a metal locating ring on the back to lock the Apple wireless charger. The thickness of the case is about 2 mm. Figure 9 shows the charge time is almost identical with or without the phone case while using the Apple wireless charger with the iPhone. So there is no need to remove the plastic phone case for wireless charging.

Figure 9 Wireless charging of iPhone with and without the phone case.

2. Charging Power: Why wired charging is much faster than wireless charging? Figure 10 shows different charging power over time with different charging options. The blue plot is for wired charging. It shows the instantaneous charging power changes over time. The phone charging algorithm is designed to provide higher charging power while the battery is very low, and lower charging power while the battery has more energy. Most importantly, the wired charging power is significantly higher (~2X) than wireless charging power, both in red plot with Apple MagSafe pad or green with Anker pad. This explains the much reduced charging time (increased charging speed) with wired charging.

There is another interesting observation comparing charging power with Apple MagSafe and Anker pads. Both demand very similar input charging power from the wall adapter DC source point of view. However, the charging time with the Anker pad is 1.5X of the time with the Apple MagSafe pad to achieve the same 20%-to-80% charge process. It means the **Anker wireless charger uses 50% more electrical energy** to achieve the same result. So from the charging speed and energy efficiency point of view, there is a good justification to have the more expensive Apple MagSafe charger than the cheaper Anker Powerwave charger.

Figure 10. Charging Power vs. Charging Time for Different Charging Methods (iPhone)

3. Energy Efficiency: Next, let's look at the comparison in terms of energy efficiency. Figure 11 shows the total electrical energy consumed to charge the iPhone 13 from 20% to 80% with three different charging options. Surprisingly, the wireless charging with Apple MagSafe pad only consumed 10% more energy than the wired charging. It shows Apple really optimized their wireless charging in terms of energy efficiency. So the additional wireless power transfer stages have a pretty good efficiency at about 90%. In comparison, wireless charging with the Qi-compatible **Anker pad consumes 50% more energy** than wired charging. The additional wireless power transfer stage therefore has an estimated poor efficiency at about 66%. So this Qi-compatible charger is much less energy or environmentally friendly than the first two options.

Figure 11. Total energy consumption comparison with different charging methods

4. **Thermal stress:** there is another noticeable performance difference – **thermal stress**. The phone is noticeably hotter (~20 degrees C) at the end of charging with the Anker wireless charger than the wired charging or Apple MagSafe wireless charging. This is understandable as the Anker charger consumes 50% more energy, resulting in additional power (heat) dissipation. This can be a concern of the cell phone's lithium-ion **battery life**, as it can be reduced especially with a fully charged battery at higher temperature.
5. **Electromagnetic radiation:** conceptually, wireless charging can generate stronger electromagnetic radiation than wired charging as the energy transfers in space without a wired connection. To quantify this, the author measured the near field EM (electromagnetic) energy by placing an EM field tester S8602 next to the phone with different charging methods. The smartphone’s charging level is about 65% in this test. The device shows a non-detectable magnetic field with wired charging, a 109.5mG magnetic field strength with the Apple wireless charger, and a 74.3mG magnetic field strength with the Anker wireless charger. Although this testing method is not perfectly accurate, it confirms a stronger EM field generated by wireless charging. Will there be health risks? The author finds no alarming information about health risks with wireless smartphone charging through internet research. Still, the author thinks it may not be the best idea to place a wireless charging pad near the bed during overnight charging.

(a) Wired Charging (b) Wireless-Apple Charger (c) Wireless-Anker Charger

Figure 12. Near Field Electromagnetic Test with Different Charging Methods

4. DISCUSSION

Different wired and wireless charging methods’ performances are studied compared in experiments using an iPhone 13 with following observations: 1) wired charging offers the fastest charging speed. In comparison, wireless charging can take 2.5X – 3.75X time. 2) wireless charging can consume more electrical energy. The Apple MagSafe charger consumes 10% more energy with an iPhone than wired charging. However, 50% more energy can be consumed and wasted by a cheaper, non-Apple wireless charger in the test. 3) more energy consumption also means more power (heat) dissipation which can potentially reduce the battery life. 4) stronger EM field energy is detected with wireless charging as expected.

What are the conclusions from this study? It remains a personal choice to select wired or wireless charging. But people should be mindful of the extra time and electrical energy as the price of the convenience of not plugging in a cable, especially if you are a technical person. In case you want to use wireless charging, keep in mind “you got what you paid for”. - The Apple MagSafe wireless charger is better suited for an iPhone device despite its higher cost than other compatible wireless chargers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge **Dr. Ming Lu**'s guidance and review of this experimental research. He provided in-depth experience in the power management field, especially in the specifics of battery charging. Dr Lu received a Ph.D. EE degree in Power Electronics from the Center of Power Electronics Systems, an NFS research center in the Virginia Polytechnic and State University. Dr Lu is currently a principal power engineer with Analog Devices Inc. (ADI), an S&P 500 and leading power management company.

References